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Original article

Effects of mindfulness and exercise on cognition and emotion in adults with mild deficits in the chronic post-stroke phase: A randomized controlled trial

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ABSTRACT

Background: Individuals with stroke often face cognitive and emotional challenges. Mindfulness-based stress reduction (MBSR), physical exercise (PE), and computerized cognitive training (CCT) are promising approaches to incorporate into post-stroke rehabilitation.

Objectives: To determine whether adding MBSR or PE to CCT improves cognition and mental health more than CCT alone, and whether any benefits are mediated by gains in mindfulness or fitness.

Methods: The MindFit Project was a single-blind, parallel, 3-arm randomized controlled trial enrolling participants with chronic stroke, assigned to MBSR + CCT, PE + CCT, or CCT-only (1:1:1). All 12-week, home-based interventions were delivered online, with 5 sessions per week. The primary outcomes included 3 cognitive and 2 mental health measures; mindfulness and physical fitness were also assessed. Analyses used per-protocol and intention-to-treat approaches.

Results: A total of 141 individuals (mean [SD] age 57.7 [11.2] years; 40 % women) were randomly assigned to 3 groups (47 each). Participants were 28.54 (20.35) months post-stroke with a mean modified Rankin Scale score of 2.23 (1.04). Of these, 78 % (39 in MBSR + CCT, 34 in PE + CCT, and 37 in CCT-only) achieved an adherence rate of ≥ 80 % and were included in the per-protocol analysis. No significant between-group differences were found in primary outcomes (all $P > 0.05$). For secondary outcomes, the PE + CCT group showed significantly greater gains in leg strength than the others ($F = 7.50$, adjusted $P = 0.009$). These results were consistent with the intention-to-treat analysis. In the per-protocol sample, improvements in mindfulness significantly mediated emotional outcomes in the MBSR + CCT group ($B = -1.08$; 95 % bootstrapped CI, -2.77 to -0.01).

Abbreviations: 2MST, 2-minute step test; 30ACT, 30-second arm curl test; 30CST, 30-second chair stand test; 8FUGT, 8-foot up and go test; ANCOVA, analysis of covariance; BDI-II, Beck depression inventory-ii; BNT-15, Boston naming test (15 items); BST, back-scratch test; CC, complete-case; CCT, computerized cognitive training; CI, confidence interval; COVID-19, coronavirus disease 2019; CSRT, chair sit and reach test; DASS-21, depression anxiety stress scales (21 items); EFA, exploratory factor analysis; FFMQ, five facet mindfulness questionnaire; GNPT, Guttmann neuro personal trainer; IIT, intention-to-treat; MAAS, mindful attention awareness scale; MBSR, mindfulness-based stress reduction; MCID, minimal clinically important difference; MD, mean difference; PE, physical exercise; PP, per-protocol; RCT, randomized controlled trial; SD, standard deviation; SFT, senior fitness test; TMT, trail making test

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Conclusions: In participants with predominantly mild chronic post-stroke deficits, adding MBSR or PE to CCT did not improve primary cognitive or emotional outcomes beyond CCT alone. However, PE + CCT increased fitness, and MBSR + CCT yielded mindfulness-mediated emotional gains. Future studies involving larger and more severe stroke samples are needed.

Trial registration: NCT04759950 (www.ClinicalTrials.gov).

Introduction

Stroke remains a leading cause of long-term disability worldwide [1]. Many individuals with stroke endure chronic physical, cognitive, and emotional impairments that diminish function and increase the risks of mortality and dementia [2,3]. Hence, timely, effective rehabilitation strategies are required to support recovery, prevent post-stroke decline, and enhance daily living.

Interest in mindfulness-based interventions, such as mindfulness-based stress reduction (MBSR) [4] and physical exercise (PE) programs, for stroke rehabilitation has grown significantly. Mindfulness training can reduce depressive symptoms, alleviate fatigue, and improve sensorimotor functions in people with stroke [5–7]. Similarly, PE can reduce depressive symptoms, enhance quality of life, and boost physical fitness [8–10]. However, most systematic reviews and meta-analyses [5–10] report inconsistent findings and call for high-quality studies to confirm these benefits.

Research into the cognitive benefits of mindfulness after stroke remains limited. Mindfulness may offer cognitive advantages, particularly in tasks that involve attention and working memory [11,12]. However, benefits have typically been observed when compared to inactive control groups in other populations [13]. Systematic reviews and meta-analyses have reported benefits in attention and processing speed following PE in individuals with stroke. Although rigorous randomized controlled trials (RCTs) are scarce [14], findings of a recent RCT showed significant cognitive gains after a 6-month multicomponent PE program [15].

A meta-analysis of computerized cognitive training (CCT), a structured and adaptive intervention widely used in neurorehabilitation, demonstrated that CCT improves post-stroke cognition [16]. Combining CCT with MBSR or PE may offer additional or synergistic benefits in stroke recovery. To date, few studies have shown that PE combined with cognitive training outperforms either intervention alone in individuals with stroke [17], and no studies have investigated the effects of combining MBSR with cognitive training in this population.

The MindFit Project [18] was a RCT designed to test whether combining MBSR or PE with CCT would yield superior cognitive and emotional improvements over CCT alone. Additionally, the project examined potential differences in outcomes between participants undergoing MBSR + CCT and PE + CCT based on their expected distinct mechanisms of action. This manuscript presents the trial's primary cognitive and emotional outcomes and tests whether changes in mindfulness and physical fitness mediate these effects. It differs from earlier MindFit publications, which addressed a qualitative sub-study [19] and a molecular biomarker analysis [20], with no overlap. In the present study, we anticipated improvements across all groups and hypothesized that MBSR would predominantly enhance emotional health while PE would primarily boost cognitive performance. Moreover, we expected that mindfulness gains in the MBSR + CCT group and fitness improvements in the PE + CCT group would specifically mediate these differential benefits.

Methods

Design and setting

The MindFit Project was a single-blind, parallel, 3-arm RCT conducted by the Faculty of Psychology at the University of Barcelona in collaboration with Hospital Germans Trias i Pujol and the Institute Guttmann. One hundred forty-one participants with chronic stroke were

randomly allocated in a 1:1:1 ratio to receive MBSR + CCT, PE + CCT, or CCT-only. The primary aims were to evaluate whether the combined interventions were superior to CCT alone in terms of cognitive and emotional outcomes, and to compare these outcomes between the 2 combined groups. Interventions lasted 12 weeks, with assessments at baseline and post-intervention. Due to the coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic, all interventions and most assessments were conducted online. The ethics committee approval and participant consents were obtained. The study protocol was registered on ClinicalTrials.gov (NCT04759950) and has been published [18]. This report adheres to the CONSORT guidelines for RCTs.

Recruitment

Participants were recruited between June 2020 and February 2021 through various channels, including social media outreach, stroke clinics, and relevant associations.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Inclusion criteria were: (1) men and women aged 18–80 years; (2) diagnosis of ischemic or hemorrhagic stroke; (3) stroke diagnosis between 3 and 60 months; (4) medical clearance to participate in an exercise intervention; and (5) fluency in Catalan or Spanish. Exclusion criteria were: (1) cognitive impairment (mini-mental state examination [21] score ≤ 23); (2) severe aphasia; (3) severe sensory deficits; (4) diagnosis of transient ischemic attack without brain lesion evidence; (5) other neurological conditions; (6) severe psychiatric disorders pre-dating stroke; and (7) history of alcohol or substance abuse.

Randomization and blinding

Participants were randomly assigned in a 1:1:1 ratio using a sequence generated by an independent biostatistician. To ensure allocation concealment, this sequence was centrally stored on a password-protected server, accessible only to an independent staff member not involved in the trial's conduct. After baseline assessments were completed, trial personnel contacted this staff member to disclose the allocation. Because the nature of the interventions precluded masking of participants, care providers, and some investigators, only outcome assessors and data analysts were blinded to treatment allocation. Masking was incorrectly registered on ClinicalTrials.gov as "Double (investigator, outcome assessor)," but the correct designation, consistent with the approved protocol [18], is "Single (outcome assessor)." Full details of randomization, allocation, and blinding are provided in Appendix A.

Interventions

The study comprised 3 intervention arms: 2 combined intervention groups (MBSR + CCT and PE + CCT) and 1 CCT-only group, each participating in a 12-week program with 5 sessions per week.

The MBSR intervention, led by an accredited mindfulness instructor, adhered to Kabat-Zinn's original protocol [4], with minor adaptations, and incorporated guided meditation (eg, body scanning, breathing exercises), gentle Hatha yoga, and daily mindfulness practices. The standard 8-week program was extended to 12 weeks by adding an introductory session in the first week, scheduling a full-day session for a separate week, and incorporating 2 consolidation weeks without guided classes. Most weeks consisted of a 150-min online group session and 4

autonomous daily practice sessions, each lasting 20–40 min. Group sessions were limited to participants with stroke; caregivers joined only occasionally for technical support.

The PE intervention followed the American Stroke Association's guidelines for individuals with stroke [22] and consisted of 5 sessions per week, including 3 group videoconference sessions and 2 autonomous walking sessions. Each group session, led by a physiotherapist and a strength and conditioning specialist, focused on different fitness aspects: 2 sessions on strength, agility, and balance (60 min each) and 1 on aerobic capacity (45 min). Additionally, participants completed 2 individual 45-min, moderate-intensity walking sessions independently.

Participants in all groups completed 45-min individual sessions of computerized, home-based, multidomain cognitive training, 5 days per week, using the Gutmann NeuroPersonalTrainer (GNPT) software [23]. Tasks targeted executive function, memory, and attention; difficulty levels were progressively adjusted according to each participant's baseline cognitive performance and real-time task outcomes.

In the combined therapy groups, participants did not receive specific guidance on the sequence of interventions. Their weekly workload approximately doubled that of the CCT-only group. Both mindfulness and PE sessions were conducted via Zoom, with groups of 8 to 12 participants. In contrast, the CCT-only group did not participate in group sessions and thus lacked a structured social component. To control for potential social support confounders in combined intervention groups, participants across all groups were encouraged to interact and share experiences through WhatsApp groups exclusive to their intervention arm. Although each arm had its own WhatsApp group for spontaneous peer support, the study team did not monitor group activity.

Appendix B provides detailed information on the materials, accommodations, exercises, and workload progression.

Intervention adherence and safety

Participants were instructed to report any adverse events spontaneously. Instructors monitored adherence to interventions by recording participant attendance during supervised sessions. Additionally, participants maintained diaries to document their autonomous sessions, recording any difficulties or adverse events they encountered, which instructors reviewed weekly.

Adherence to the PE and CCT interventions was defined as the ratio of completed sessions to the total number of planned sessions. MBSR adherence was quantified based on the total time participants spent engaging in the program relative to its planned duration. For participants in the combined intervention groups, overall adherence was calculated as the arithmetic mean of the adherence rates for each component intervention. Following standard practice, participants with an overall adherence rate of $\geq 80\%$ were considered adherent.

Baseline measures

Demographic characteristics were collected using Microsoft Forms, provided under the University of Barcelona's institutional license. A physician recorded participants' stroke data, medical diagnoses, and medication use during an initial online medical visit. Stroke-related impairments were assessed using the National Institutes of Health Stroke Scale [24]. Functional independence was assessed using the Barthel Index [25], and disability was assessed using the Modified Rankin Scale [26].

Outcomes

This paper reports on the MindFit Project's pre-specified primary outcomes, which include cognitive factors and 2 mental health scores. Changes in mindfulness and fitness variables were also evaluated.

Measurements were taken within 15 days before and after the intervention period. Due to COVID-19 restrictions, all assessments were

conducted online, adhering to the guidelines typically applied to in-person evaluations. Before the trial, pilot tests were performed to verify the reliability of the remote cognitive and physical assessments. The same evaluator conducted assessments at both time points. Participants received instructions, access links, and reminders before each assessment session. Support persons, when needed, were briefed to ensure they minimized any interference during the assessments. Questionnaires were administered using Microsoft Forms.

Performance-based cognitive measures

A comprehensive battery of standardized cognitive tests was administered, comprising the Boston Naming Test-15 (BNT-15) [27], Rey Auditory Verbal Learning Test [28], Rey-Osterrieth Complex Figure [29], Stroop Color and Word Test [30], Trail Making Test (TMT) A and B [31], Verbal Fluency Test (letter and category fluency) [32], and selected subtests from the Wechsler Adult Intelligence Scale-III [33], including Digits, Digit Symbol Coding, Matrix, and Vocabulary. A licensed neuropsychologist conducted all assessments via the business version of Zoom. Details on adapting cognitive testing to an online format are provided in Appendix C. Factor analysis was applied to individual test scores to derive primary cognitive outcomes, rather than the theory-driven composite scores proposed in the protocol [18]. This refinement, aimed at improving construct validity, was made after data collection but before testing intervention effects.

Mental health questionnaires

Two standardized instruments were used to assess mental health: the Beck Depression Inventory-II (BDI-II) [34], a 21-item self-report tool designed to determine the severity of depressive symptoms, and the Depression, Anxiety, and Stress Scales-21 (DASS-21) [35], which evaluates depression, anxiety, and stress across 3, 7-item subscales. For this study, the primary mental health outcomes were the BDI-II score and the DASS-21 global score, the sum of the scores for the 3 subscales. Emotional outcomes were listed as primary outcomes in the protocol [18] but not on [ClinicalTrials.gov](https://www.clinicaltrials.gov), due to a registration oversight.

Mindfulness measures

Changes in mindfulness were assessed using 2 widely recognized self-report tools: the Mindful Attention Awareness Scale (MAAS) [36] and the Five-Facet Mindfulness Questionnaire (FFMQ) [37]. The MAAS is a unidimensional, 15-item scale that measures attention to and awareness of the present moment. The 39-item FFMQ assesses mindfulness across 5 dimensions: observing, describing, acting with awareness, non-reactivity, and non-judging.

Physical fitness

The Senior Fitness Test (SFT) [38] was used to assess physical fitness through 6 standardized measures: 30-second Chair Stand Test (30CST; lower-body strength), 30-second Arm Curl Test (30ACT; upper-body strength), 2-minute Step Test (2MST; aerobic capacity), Chair Sit and Reach Test (CSRT; lower-body flexibility), Back-Scratch Test (BST; upper-body flexibility), and 8-Foot Up and Go Test (8FUGT; agility and balance). Although primarily for older adults, the SFT has been proven feasible, safe, and valuable in people with stroke [39]. A trained physiotherapist conducted all assessments remotely via a hospital-specific telematics platform, strictly following the official SFT guidelines. Previous studies have validated that online functional assessments yield results comparable to in-person tests [40].

Statistical analysis

Statistical analyses were conducted using IBM SPSS (v.29) and R (v.4.3.2), with significance set at 2-tailed $P < 0.05$. It was determined that including 47 participants per group (across 3 groups) was necessary to achieve 80% power to detect a between-group difference of 0.75 standard deviations (SD) at a 2-tailed alpha level of 0.05, accounting for a

20 % expected dropout rate. This effect size was chosen based on previous findings regarding the impact of mindfulness and PE interventions on cognitive and emotional outcomes among individuals with stroke [18].

An exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was conducted to identify the underlying structure in baseline cognitive scores. The suitability of data for EFA was confirmed using Bartlett's test of sphericity and the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure. Principal axis factoring with direct oblimin rotation was used to analyze standardized test scores. Factors were retained based on parallel analysis, and significant factor loadings were set at ≥ 0.40 . Factor scores were calculated using the regression method, and baseline factor coefficients were also applied to standardized post-intervention scores. Further methodological details can be found in Appendix D.

This study focused on 10 main variables: 5 pre-specified primary outcomes (3 cognitive factors, BDI-II, and global DASS-21) and 5 additional intervention-related measures formally classified as secondary outcomes. The latter included 2 mindfulness measures (MAAS and global FFMQ) and 3 physical fitness tests (30CST, 30ACT, and 2MST). For clarity and consistency, we refer to this full set of 10 variables as the "main variables." These were the only variables for which cross-outcome significance adjustments and multiple imputation were applied. All other measures, including individual cognitive test scores, questionnaire subscales, and the remaining SFT components, are referred to as "secondary variables" and were analyzed in an exploratory manner.

Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was the pre-specified method used to evaluate the efficacy of the interventions. The dependent variable was the change score (post-intervention minus baseline), and the intervention group was included as a fixed factor. Covariates included in the analysis were age, sex, years of education, time since stroke, and baseline scores. Before conducting analyses, the statistical assumptions for ANCOVA were checked. Post hoc pairwise comparisons were conducted for significant ANCOVA results. Additionally, within-group comparisons between baseline and post-intervention were performed using paired *t*-tests.

To control the family-wise error rate across the 10 main outcome variables, while maintaining statistical power, *P*-values and confidence intervals (CIs) were adjusted using the Holm-Bonferroni method, which is less conservative than the Bonferroni correction. Due to its stricter control over error rates, the Bonferroni correction was reserved for post hoc pairwise comparisons within each outcome. Cross-outcome adjustments were not applied for exploratory analyses on secondary variables and mediation models, although Bonferroni corrections were used within each outcome for pairwise comparisons.

Mediation analyses were pre-specified and conducted using the PROCESS macro in R to examine whether specific mindfulness and physical fitness variables with significant group differences mediated the primary outcomes. Following recent recommendations, we tested mediation regardless of whether the interventions showed a statistically significant total effect on the primary outcomes, as indirect effects can still occur (eg, cases of inconsistent mediation) [41]. Dummy coding was used to include the intervention group as a multicategorical independent variable. Covariates were the same as those used in the ANCOVA models. Significance was assessed using a percentile bootstrap with 10,000 resamples and a 95 % CI adjusted by the Bonferroni correction. A seed was set to enhance reproducibility.

As described in the study protocol [18], both per-protocol (PP) and intention-to-treat (ITT) analyses were pre-specified. The PP analysis included participants with data at both time points and ≥ 80 % adherence to the intervention. For ITT, the protocol allowed either a complete-case (CC) approach or multiple imputation, depending on the extent and nature of the missing data. To preserve statistical power and minimize the bias introduced by listwise deletion, since CC deviates from the ITT principle, missing data for the 10 main variables were imputed under the assumption of missing at random. Missing values were addressed using multivariate imputation by chained equations

with predictive mean matching, implemented with the mice package in R. A total of 100 imputed datasets were generated, and ANCOVA results were pooled according to Rubin's rules. Further details are available in Appendix E. A CC analysis was also performed and is reported as a reference. Secondary outcomes and mediation models were analyzed using only PP and CC approaches.

Results based on the PP sample are presented in the main text, while results from the CC and ITT analyses are discussed briefly in the main text and detailed in the appendices.

Results

Participants

Out of 412 individuals screened, 141 were randomly assigned to the 3 intervention arms in a 1:1:1 ratio. Individuals not enrolled were excluded due to disinterest or ineligibility (Fig. 1). During the study, 14 participants (10 % attrition rate) were lost to follow-up: 4 in each of the MBSR + CCT and PE + CCT groups (9 % for each) and 6 in the CCT-only group (13 %). Dropouts were attributed to health-related issues unrelated to the interventions or other personal matters (Fig. 1 and Table E1). Among the 127 participants who completed the study, 17 were excluded from the PP analysis because they failed to meet the minimum intervention adherence threshold of 80 %.

Table 1 presents demographic and clinical information for the 110 participants in the PP sample. Given the randomized allocation to intervention groups, no formal tests were conducted to assess baseline differences among groups [42]. Descriptive statistics for the CC and ITT samples are detailed in Appendix F (Table F1). Importantly, no significant differences were observed among the PP, CC, and ITT samples (Table F2).

Due to COVID-19-related delays, 2 participants in the PE + CCT group exceeded the age limit of 80 years, and 11 participants (4 in MBSR + CCT, 5 in PE + CCT, and 2 in CCT-only) exceeded the chronicity limit of 60 months at the time of baseline assessment, although all were eligible at recruitment. They were retained, though given the relative arbitrariness of these cutoffs, sensitivity analyses excluding them were also conducted (see below).

Intervention adherence and safety

Adherence rates for each intervention group across the PP, CC, and ITT samples are detailed in Appendix G (Table G1). The mean (SD) adherence rates for the 3 groups were: MBSR + CCT, 83 % (23 %); PE + CCT, 82 % (22 %); and CCT-only, 85 % (28 %). Notably, 78 % of all participants ($n = 110$) maintained adherence above the 80 % threshold.

During the intervention period, 6 adverse events were reported: 2 in the MBSR + CCT group (toe amputation and COVID-19 hospitalization), 1 in the PE + CCT group (hemorrhoid surgery), and 3 in the CCT-only group (hospitalization for an unknown disease, an ischemic stroke, and death due to hemorrhagic stroke). There were no reports of additional events such as fatigue, pain, or falls. An independent safety monitor determined that no adverse events were related to the study interventions.

EFA of cognitive measures

The EFA of cognitive measures identified 3 factors, which we labeled as Verbal Executive Functioning, Verbal Memory, and Visual Executive Functioning. Together, these 3 factors explained 69 % of the total variance, with individual contributions of Verbal Executive Functioning (43 %), Verbal Memory (14 %), and Visual Executive Functioning (12 %). The factor structure is illustrated in Fig. 2. Appendix D provides additional details on data suitability and further EFA results.

Fig. 1. MindFit trial flow diagram. CC-A, complete-case analysis; CCT, computerized cognitive training; ITT-A, intention-to-treat analysis; MBSR, mindfulness-based stress reduction; PE, physical exercise; PP-A, per protocol analysis.

Table 1
Participants' characteristics by treatment group (per-protocol sample).

	MBSR + CCT (n = 39)	PE + CCT (n = 34)	CCT-only (n = 37)
Age, y ^a	55.5 (10.7)	58.8 (12.0)	58.7 (8.5)
Sex, n (%)			
Female	20 (51)	14 (41)	13 (35)
Male	19 (49)	20 (59)	24 (65)
Education, y	12.54 (3.02)	13.09 (4.00)	11.59 (3.33)
Number of strokes	1.05 (0.22)	1.12 (0.48)	1.14 (0.35)
Time since the stroke, mo ^b	33.96 (21.66)	26.72 (18.91)	21.02 (16.30)
Type of stroke, n (%)			
Ischemic	24 (62)	26 (76)	25 (68)
Intracerebral hemorrhage	11 (28)	7 (21)	10 (27)
Subarachnoid hemorrhage	4 (10)	1 (3)	2 (5)
Circulation, n (%)			
Anterior	30 (77)	21 (62)	25 (68)
Posterior	9 (23)	13 (38)	10 (27)
Unknown	0 (0)	0 (0)	2 (5)
Laterality, n (%)			
Right	19 (49)	8 (23)	18 (49)
Left	15 (38)	23 (68)	17 (46)
Bilateral	4 (10)	3 (9)	2 (5)
Unknown	1 (3)	0 (0)	0 (0)
National institute of health stroke scale (0–42) ^b	2.87 (3.33)	2.24 (2.52)	3.05 (3.36)
Modified Rankin scale (0–6) ^c	2.26 (1.04)	2.06 (0.89)	2.46 (1.10)
Barthel index (0–100) ^d	91.54 (17.48)	95.00 (10.66)	92.70 (14.07)
Mini-mental state examination (0–30) ^e	28.46 (1.71)	28.85 (1.23)	28.57 (1.21)
WAIS-III - vocabulary subtest (0–66) ^f	46.69 (11.03)	46.47 (11.28)	43.68 (8.75)

Abbreviations: CCT, computerized cognitive training; MBSR, mindfulness-based stress reduction; PE, physical exercise; WAIS-III, Weschler adult intelligence scale-III.

Note: Data are presented as M (SD) unless otherwise indicated.

^a Due to delays associated with the coronavirus disease 2019 pandemic and the time lapse between recruitment and randomization, two participants in the PE + CCT group exceeded the upper age limit of 80 years, and 11 participants (four in the MBSR + CCT group, five in the PE + CCT group, and two in the CCT-only group) exceeded the maximum stroke chronicity limit of 60 months.

^b The National Institutes of Health Stroke Scale ranges from 0 to 42, with higher scores indicating greater stroke severity.

^c The modified Rankin Scale ranges from 0 to 5, with higher scores indicating greater disability.

^d The Barthel Index scores range from 0 to 100, with higher scores indicating greater independence.

^e The Mini-Mental State Examination scores range from 0 to 30, with a score of 24–30 indicating normal cognitive function.

^f The WAIS-III Vocabulary subtest scores range from 0 to 66, with higher scores indicating greater vocabulary proficiency. This subtest is commonly used as an estimate of premorbid intelligence.

Intervention-related changes in the ten main variables

ANCOVA models revealed no significant between-group differences in the 5 primary outcomes, including cognitive factors and mental health scores (Table 2). Among the 5 intervention-related secondary variables focused on mindfulness and fitness, a significant between-group difference was observed in leg strength (30CST), and this difference remained significant after correction for multiple comparisons. Post hoc Bonferroni-corrected analyses revealed that the PE + CCT group demonstrated a significantly greater increase in lower-body strength compared to the other groups. This result was consistent with the findings from CC and ITT (Tables H1–H2 and Figure H1).

Other between-group differences in upper-body strength (30ACT), aerobic capacity (2MST), and global FFMQ scores were observed but did not remain significant after adjustment for multiple comparisons. Despite this, Bonferroni-corrected post hoc comparisons revealed that the PE + CCT group demonstrated significantly greater improvements in upper-body strength and aerobic capacity compared to the other groups. Additionally, the MBSR + CCT group exhibited a significantly greater improvement in FFMQ score compared to the CCT-only group. Because these pairwise comparisons were conducted in the context of a non-significant omnibus test after adjustment, the findings should be interpreted cautiously as potential trends rather than definitive results. Notably, the observed

effects in 2MST persisted in CC and ITT analyses, whereas differences in FFMQ and 30ACT disappeared (Appendix H).

We conducted 3 exploratory sensitivity analyses to assess the robustness of the primary ANCOVA results (Appendix H). First, we re-estimated all models in the strictly eligible sample by excluding 13 participants who exceeded the age or chronicity cutoffs. The pattern of between-group effects remained unchanged (Table H3). Second, to address baseline imbalance in depression scores, we re-ran the full-sample models including baseline BDI-II scores as an additional covariate. Effect estimates were consistent with the primary analyses (Figure H2). Third, we examined the potential influence of intervention engagement by adding overall adherence and an adherence-by-group interaction term to the models. This addition did not meaningfully alter any of the 10 outcome comparisons (Table H4).

Paired-sample *t*-tests conducted within each group (Table 2) indicated significant improvements in primary cognitive outcomes across all groups, with most findings retaining significance after adjustment for multiple comparisons. In contrast, significant reductions in mental health outcomes were exclusively observed in the MBSR + CCT group. The CCT-only group experienced a more minor, non-significant decrease in BDI-II score post-adjustment, and no significant emotional improvements were noted in the PE + CCT group. Notably, enhanced mindfulness was only significant in the MBSR + CCT group, while fitness-related improvements were confined to the PE

Fig. 2. Exploratory factor analysis results. An exploratory factor analysis was conducted using principal axis factoring with direct oblimin rotation to uncover the structure of baseline cognitive scores. The figure displays factor loadings for each cognitive test, grouped into 3 identified factors. Blue bars indicate significant loadings (≥ 0.40), with dashed lines marking the threshold for factor significance. COWAT, controlled oral word association test (phonemic verbal fluency task); RAVLT, Rey auditory verbal learning test; ROCF, Rey-osterrieth complex-figure.

+ CCT group. These findings were consistent across the CC and ITT samples (Tables H5–H6).

Intervention-related changes in secondary variables

ANCOVA models for secondary variables in the PP sample (Appendix I, Tables I1–I2) revealed significant between-group differences in changes in TMT-B ($F[2, 100] = 3.68, P = 0.029, \eta_p^2 = 0.07$), BNT-15 ($F[2, 101] = 3.13, P = 0.048, \eta_p^2 = 0.06$), and the observing ($F[2, 102] = 3.75, P = 0.027, \eta_p^2 = 0.07$) and non-reactivity facets of the FFMQ ($F[2, 102] = 3.58, P = 0.031, \eta_p^2 = 0.07$). No significant differences were observed in fitness variables related to flexibility and balance.

Post hoc analyses with Bonferroni adjustment showed that the PE + CCT group demonstrated significantly greater improvement in TMT-B than the MBSR + CCT group (adjusted mean difference [MD] = 37.43 s [95 % CI: 2.16, 72.69 s], $P_{adj} = 0.034, d = 0.64$). In contrast, the MBSR + CCT group showed significantly greater improvements than the CCT-only group in the observing facet of mindfulness (adjusted MD = 0.46 [95 % CI: 0.05, 0.88], $P_{adj} = 0.024, d = 0.66$). The pairwise comparisons for BNT-15 and the non-reactivity facet of mindfulness did not reach statistical significance after correction. Notably, the between-group differences observed in the PP sample were not significant in the CC sample (Table I3).

Results of within-group paired-sample *t*-tests for secondary variables, which closely resemble those obtained in the within-group analyses of the 10 main variables, are presented in Tables I4 (PP sample) and Table I5 (CC sample).

Mediation analysis

Mediation analyses were conducted to examine whether changes in mindfulness scores and fitness test results, which showed significant between-group differences, served as potential mediators. Among the models tested, we observed a statistically significant mediation effect in the PP sample (Fig. 3). Compared to the PE + CCT group, participants in the MBSR + CCT group showed a 1.08-unit reduction in BDI-II score [95 % adjusted bootstrapped CI: -2.77 to -0.01], driven by an increase in FFMQ score, which in turn contributed to a reduction in depression symptoms (Fig. 3B). A similar trend emerged when comparing the MBSR + CCT group to the CCT-only group, though this effect approached but did not reach significance (Fig. 3A). In contrast, no mindfulness-related mediation effect on depression score was detected when comparing PE + CCT with CCT-only. The analysis of the CC data did not detect this mindfulness-related mediation effect on depression scores, as detailed in Table J1.

Discussion

This study aimed to assess the cognitive and emotional changes induced by combining MBSR or PE with CCT compared to those of CCT alone. The combined interventions did not significantly improve primary cognitive and emotional outcomes compared to CCT-only. However, evidence from within-group pre-post comparisons and exploratory analyses suggested some specific benefits of MBSR (emotional) and PE (cognitive) outcomes. Moreover, each combined intervention showed specific benefits in its target domain: MBSR + CCT improved mindfulness, and PE + CCT enhanced physical fitness. Improvements in

Table 2
Within-group changes and between-group differences in the 10 main variables.

Domain/variable	Descriptives			Within-group changes (T1 – T0)						Between-group omnibus test				Post hoc comparisons					
	n ^a	T0	T1	M (SD)	95 % CI ^b	t	P	P _{adj} ^b	d	M _{adj} (SE) ^c	F	P	P _{adj} ^b	n _p ²	Contrast	Adj MD (95 % CI) ^d	P	P _{adj} ^d	d
Cognition^e																			
Verbal EEEF																			
MBSR + CCT (G1)	39	0.17 (1.07)	0.40 (1.15)	0.23 (0.42)	0.01, 0.44	3.40	0.002	0.030	0.54	0.22 (0.06)	0.09	0.912	1.000	0.00					
PE + CCT (G2)	33	0.10 (0.86)	0.31 (0.84)	0.20 (0.39)	-0.01, 0.42	3.00	0.005	0.087	0.52	0.21 (0.07)									
CCT-only (G3)	36	-0.18 (0.83)	0.08 (0.89)	0.26 (0.31)	0.09, 0.43	5.07	<0.001	<0.001	0.84	0.25 (0.07)									
Verbal memory																			
MBSR + CCT (G1)	39	0.22 (0.98)	0.72 (1.16)	0.50 (0.55)	0.20, 0.80	5.69	<0.001	<0.001	0.91	0.51 (0.10)	0.89	0.414	1.000	0.02					
PE + CCT (G2)	33	0.21 (1.02)	0.55 (0.89)	0.33 (0.57)	0.01, 0.65	3.33	0.002	0.040	0.58	0.35 (0.11)									
CCT-only (G3)	37	-0.26 (0.90)	0.30 (1.12)	0.56 (0.72)	0.17, 0.96	4.76	<0.001	<0.001	0.78	0.54 (0.11)									
Visual EEEF																			
MBSR + CCT (G1)	32	0.14 (0.94)	0.23 (1.06)	0.09 (0.38)	-0.11, 0.30	1.39	0.173	1.000	0.25	0.12 (0.06)	2.10	0.129	0.646	0.05					
PE + CCT (G2)	27	0.05 (0.57)	0.33 (0.56)	0.28 (0.30)	0.08, 0.47	4.75	<0.001	0.002	0.91	0.29 (0.06)									
CCT-only (G3)	31	0.18 (0.67)	0.36 (0.59)	0.18 (0.34)	-0.02, 0.38	2.90	0.007	0.112	0.52	0.14 (0.06)									
Mental health^f																			
BDI-II (0–63)																			
MBSR + CCT (G1)	39	18.36 (10.09)	13.54 (10.03)	-4.82 (6.06)	-8.07, -1.57	-4.97	<0.001	<0.001	-0.80	-3.62 (0.98)	2.49	0.088	0.529	0.05					
PE + CCT (G2)	34	11.47 (7.08)	11.62 (7.16)	0.15 (5.16)	-1.65, 1.95	0.17	0.869	1.000	0.03	-0.64 (1.06)									
CCT-only (G3)	37	17.11 (10.33)	14.24 (10.33)	-2.86 (7.75)	-6.87, 1.14	-2.25	0.031	0.460	-0.37	-3.40 (1.01)									
Mental health^g																			
DASS-21 (0–126)																			
MBSR + CCT (G1)	39	50.00 (25.94)	40.67 (25.67)	-9.33 (16.56)	-17.92, -0.74	-3.52	0.001	0.023	-0.56	-6.45 (2.73)	0.12	0.889	1.000	0.00					
PE + CCT (G2)	34	33.06 (21.42)	31.18 (19.96)	-1.88 (18.85)	-10.96, 7.19	-0.58	0.564	1.000	-0.10	-4.51 (2.95)									
CCT-only (G3)	37	49.14 (25.98)	44.59 (26.73)	-4.54 (18.47)	-13.92, 4.84	-1.50	0.143	1.000	-0.25	-5.16 (2.82)									
Mindfulness^h																			
MAAS (1–6)																			
MBSR + CCT (G1)	39	4.03 (1.08)	4.50 (1.13)	0.47 (0.77)	0.06, 0.87	3.77	<0.001	0.012	0.60	0.35 (0.12)	0.78	0.462	1.000	0.02					
PE + CCT (G2)	34	4.65 (0.96)	4.77 (0.90)	0.13 (0.74)	-0.25, 0.50	1.02	0.313	1.000	0.18	0.19 (0.13)									
CCT-only (G3)	37	4.35 (0.98)	4.42 (1.05)	0.07 (0.77)	-0.27, 0.42	0.57	0.574	1.000	0.09	0.14 (0.12)									
FFMQ (1–5)																			
MBSR + CCT (G1)	39	3.24 (0.56)	3.54 (0.60)	0.30 (0.44)	0.07, 0.54	4.28	<0.001	0.003	0.68	0.27 (0.06)	4.02	0.021	0.147	0.07	G1 vs G3	0.23 (0.02, 0.44)	0.008	0.025	0.65
PE + CCT (G2)	34	3.52 (0.56)	3.58 (0.58)	0.06 (0.32)	-0.10, 0.23	1.13	0.268	1.000	0.19	0.09 (0.06)					G2 vs G3	0.05 (-0.17, 0.27)	0.555	1.000	0.15
CCT-only (G3)	37	3.19 (0.46)	3.22 (0.45)	0.03 (0.37)	-0.13, 0.18	0.43	0.667	1.000	0.07	0.04 (0.06)					G1 vs G2	0.18 (-0.03, 0.39)	0.042	0.130	0.50
Fitnessⁱ																			
30CST, rep																			
MBSR + CCT (G1)	38	9.16 (4.12)	9.55 (4.09)	0.39 (1.97)	-0.57, 1.36	1.24	0.224	1.000	0.20	0.32 (0.30)	7.50	<0.001	0.009	0.13	G1 vs G3	0.23 (-0.84, 1.30)	0.598	1.000	0.13
PE + CCT (G2)	34	9.03 (3.74)	10.62 (4.30)	1.59 (1.78)	0.55, 2.63	5.21	<0.001	<0.001	0.89	1.64 (0.31)					G2 vs G3	1.55 (0.49, 2.61)	<0.001	0.002	0.87
CCT-only (G3)	37	8.35 (4.02)	8.41 (4.06)	0.05 (1.53)	-0.53, 0.64	0.22	0.831	1.000	0.04	0.09 (0.30)					G1 vs G2	-1.32 (-2.37, -0.27)	0.003	0.009	-0.74
Fitness^j																			
30ACT, rep																			
MBSR + CCT (G1)	38	9.79 (3.52)	9.97 (3.38)	0.18 (2.20)	-0.75, 1.12	0.52	0.609	1.000	0.08	0.23 (0.37)	5.45	0.006	0.051	0.10	G1 vs G3	-0.10 (-1.41, 1.22)	0.860	1.000	-0.04
PE + CCT (G2)	34	9.09 (3.15)	11.06 (3.81)	1.97 (2.43)	0.57, 3.37	4.73	<0.001	0.001	0.81	1.81 (0.38)					G2 vs G3	1.48 (0.17, 2.80)	0.007	0.021	0.67
CCT-only (G3)	37	9.84 (2.98)	10.05 (2.95)	0.22 (2.17)	-0.80, 1.24	0.60	0.549	1.000	0.10	0.32 (0.38)					G1 vs G2	-1.58 (-2.89, -0.28)	0.004	0.012	-0.72
2MST, step																			
MBSR + CCT (G1)	36	53.00 (21.09)	55.11 (21.27)	2.11 (15.43)	-5.37, 9.59	0.82	0.417	1.000	0.14	2.09 (2.37)	4.70	0.011	0.090	0.09	G1 vs G3	-0.98 (-9.41, 7.46)	0.779	1.000	-0.07
PE + CCT (G2)	34	54.12 (21.76)	65.15 (25.08)	11.03 (16.07)	1.91, 20.15	4.00	<0.001	0.007	0.69	11.36 (2.36)					G2 vs G3	8.29 (0.15, 16.44)	0.015	0.045	0.61
CCT-only (G3)	36	51.06 (25.75)	54.42 (22.00)	3.36 (11.45)	-2.60, 9.32	1.76	0.087	1.000	0.29	3.07 (2.36)					G1 vs G2	-9.27 (-17.47, -1.07)	0.007	0.021	-0.68

Abbreviations: 2MST, 2-minute step test; 30ACT, 30-second arm curl test; Adj, adjusted; BDI-II, Beck depression inventory-II; CCT, computerized cognitive training; CI, confidence interval; DASS-21, depression anxiety stress scales-21; FFMQ, five facet mindfulness questionnaire; MAAS, mindful attention awareness scale; MBSR, mindfulness-based stress reduction; MD, mean difference; PE, physical exercise; T0, time point 0 (baseline); T1, time point 1 (post-intervention).

Note: Adjusted and unadjusted p-values that exceed the significance threshold (< 0.05) are highlighted in bold.

^a Analyses for each variable were conducted using the complete data set available for each measure in the per-protocol sample (adherence ≥ 80 %).

^b The 95 % confidence intervals for the mean differences and the adjusted p-values for t-tests and F-tests were corrected for multiple comparisons using the Holm-Bonferroni method.

^c Means are adjusted for the following covariates: sex, age, years of education, time since stroke, and baseline value of each outcome.

^d In post hoc comparisons, the 95 % confidence intervals for the pairwise mean differences and adjusted p-values are corrected using the Bonferroni method for multiple comparisons.

^e Factor scores have a group mean of 0 and a standard deviation of approximately 1, with higher scores indicating better performance. Improvement in these factors corresponds to positive T1–T0 difference scores.

^f The Beck Depression Inventory-II scores range from 0 to 63, with higher scores indicating more severe depressive symptoms. The Depression Anxiety Stress Scales-21 total score ranges from 0 to 126, with higher scores indicating greater severity of depressive, anxiety, and stress symptoms. Improvement in these variables corresponds to negative T1–T0 difference scores.

^g The Mindful Attention Awareness Scale ranges from 1 to 6, with higher scores reflecting a greater tendency to be mindful in daily life. The Five Facet Mindfulness Questionnaire total score ranges from 1 to 5, with higher scores indicating greater mindfulness skills. Improvement in these variables corresponds to positive T1–T0 difference scores.

^h The fitness tests—the 30-second Chair Stand Test, 30-second Arm Curl Test, and 2-minute Step Test—measure lower limb strength, upper limb strength, and aerobic capacity, respectively. Higher scores indicate better performance, and positive T1–T0 difference scores represent improvement.

Fig. 3. Mediation analysis of the effect of mindfulness (FFMQ) on depression symptoms (BDI-II) in the per-protocol sample. This figure illustrates the indirect effect of changes in FFMQ scores (mindfulness) on reductions in BDI-II scores (depression symptoms) across different intervention comparisons. Panel A displays comparisons between MBSR + CCT and CCT-only and between PE + CCT and CCT-only. Panel B presents comparisons between MBSR + CCT and PE + CCT, and between CCT-only and PE + CCT. Analyses were adjusted for sex, age, education, time since stroke, and baseline BDI-II scores. Significant indirect effects are highlighted in bold. Confidence intervals (95 %) were corrected for multiple comparisons using the Bonferroni adjustment. Bootstrap confidence intervals were calculated from 10,000 resamples using the percentile method. A seed (123) was set to ensure reproducibility. BDI-II, Beck depression inventory-ii; CCT, computerized cognitive training; FFMQ, five facet mindfulness questionnaire; MBSR, mindfulness-based stress reduction; PE, physical exercise.

mindfulness mediated reductions in depressive symptoms in the MBSR + CCT group, whereas no mediation effects were found for physical fitness gains in the PE + CCT group. Each of these findings is discussed below.

Cognitive performance improvements

All groups demonstrated improvements across the 3 cognitive factor scores at 3 months, with most showing statistical significance in within-group analysis. Despite these improvements, no significant differences were observed among the groups, and this result was consistent across all analytical approaches applied: PP, CC, and ITT. The absence of a passive control group in our study design limits our ability to determine whether the similar improvements across groups were due to the CCT, natural recovery post-stroke, test-retest learning effects, or a combination of these factors.

Unexpectedly, the PE + CCT group did not exhibit greater improvements in the primary cognitive outcomes, contradicting the broader literature, which supports cognitive benefits from PE following stroke, particularly programs that combine aerobic and resistance training [14]. This discrepancy may suggest that the cognitive benefits of exercise are potentially less consistent than previously assumed, as indicated by a recent review of RCTs in healthy populations [43]. However, several factors could account for the absence of more pronounced cognitive benefits in our study.

First, although our protocol involved an intensive PE intervention with 5 sessions per week over 12 weeks, this duration may have been insufficient to observe detectable cognitive improvements. While a meta-analysis identified cognitive gains within similar timeframes [14], longer interventions may enable more significant molecular and neural adaptations that amplify cognitive outcomes. For example, findings from a recent RCT [15] show that a 6-month, twice-weekly PE intervention demonstrated significant cognitive benefits, highlighting the potential efficacy of extending the duration of interventions.

Second, our comparison between the PE + CCT and CCT-only groups was designed to isolate the cognitive benefits attributable to PE. However, a direct comparison between a PE-only group and a passive control may have provided clearer insights into the specific contributions of PE. Despite this limitation, few studies have shown cognitive advantages of a combined PE plus cognitive training approach over cognitive training alone in stroke populations [17]. The limited cognitive gains observed in our study may be attributable to a lack of structured scheduling and/or the simultaneous implementation of both interventions. Arranging CCT directly after PE may better harness the well-established acute benefits of PE [44].

Third, as highlighted in a recent review [45], baseline characteristics likely influence cognitive responses to PE interventions. Our sample varied considerably in terms of lesion location, stroke severity, and baseline cognitive function. Lifestyle factors may also play a role; in our study, some participants led sedentary lifestyles, while others maintained healthy habits after their stroke. Cognitive benefits might have been more pronounced if all participants were physically inactive and cognitively impaired at baseline, allowing for greater potential for improvement in both domains. This hypothesis is supported by a meta-analysis of cerebrovascular disorders, which indicates that individuals with baseline cognitive impairment derive the most significant cognitive benefit from PE [46].

Notably, although the differences in primary cognitive outcomes between groups were not significant, analyses at the test level revealed specific cognitive benefits attributable to the PE component. The PE + CCT group showed more significant improvements in TMT-B time than the MBSR + CCT group. These improvements, of moderate magnitude, were observed in the PP sample but not in the CC. While this discrepancy may reflect greater adherence in the former, other attrition-related biases cannot be completely ruled out. Therefore, this finding should be interpreted with caution. Nevertheless, it is worth mentioning that only the PE + CCT group exceeded the minimal clinically important difference (MCID) of -24.40 s for the TMT-B [47] in both the PP ($M = -34.06$, $M_{adj} = -38.39$) and CC samples ($M = -29.61$, $M_{adj} = -34.49$). While exploratory, these findings highlight the potential of PE interventions to effectively target specific cognitive processes (eg, mental flexibility, processing speed). The TMT-B may be a particularly sensitive test for capturing these effects.

Regarding the effects of mindfulness on cognitive functioning, we found no cognitive advantage of the MBSR + CCT intervention over CCT alone, either in composite scores or individual tests. This contrasts with previous studies in other populations, which reported modest gains from mindfulness training, particularly in working memory [11,12]. In our study, verbal working memory, assessed using the backward digit span, improved significantly within the MBSR + CCT group (small to moderate effect size). However, similar improvements in the other groups suggest this change is not specific to MBSR. Several factors may explain the absence of MBSR-specific effects, including the short duration of the intervention, limited room for improvement due to largely unimpaired baseline performance, the use of an active comparator involving cognitive training, and the potential insensitivity of our measures to subtle mindfulness-related changes. Future studies should include more comprehensive assessments of working memory, attention, and other higher-order functions such as metacognition.

Mental health improvements

Within-group analyses showed significant improvements in primary mental health outcomes and all DASS-21 subdomains in the MBSR + CCT group, only. The effect sizes were large for the BDI-II and small to moderate for the DASS-21 measures. According to the MCID for the BDI-II, as defined by Kounali et al. [48], 44 % of participants in the MBSR + CCT group experienced clinically meaningful improvement, a rate nearly matched by the CCT-only group (43 %). In contrast, the PE + CCT group showed minimal post-intervention change, with average scores remaining close to baseline and only 18 % of participants achieving clinically significant improvements in BDI-II scores.

Nevertheless, between-group comparisons revealed no significant differences in primary mental health outcomes across the PP, CC, or ITT analyses. This finding does not support our initial hypothesis, which anticipated improvements across all groups, with the most substantial gains in the MBSR + CCT group. Although prior evidence supports the efficacy of PE in addressing post-stroke depression [9], the PE + CCT group did not show significant changes. One possible explanation is that participants in this group initially reported minimal depressive symptoms, unlike the MBSR + CCT and CCT-only groups, where average baseline symptoms were in the mild range. This initial difference may have limited the potential for measurable improvement in the PE + CCT group.

Moreover, despite similar baseline mental health scores among participants in the MBSR + CCT and CCT-only groups, the anticipated greater emotional improvements in the MBSR + CCT group were not observed. Although MBSR targets stress reduction and has shown promise in treating post-stroke emotional disturbances [5,6], our active control condition (CCT-only) may also have conferred mental health benefits. This observation aligns with findings from a recent systematic review of 44 meta-analyses, which indicated that mindfulness interventions often yield more minor, less significant effects relative to active controls rather than passive ones [49]. Furthermore, qualitative data from the MindFit Project [19] suggested that participation in any structured intervention, combined with peer support, may significantly contribute to emotional well-being after stroke. It is also possible that the superiority of mindfulness interventions might become more evident in individuals with moderate to severe psychiatric symptoms; these individuals were underrepresented in this sample. Indeed, a recent study in people with post-stroke anxiety and depressive symptoms reported promising results for an adapted mindfulness intervention [50].

Mindfulness and fitness improvements and their potential mediating role

The greater improvements observed in the PP between-group analysis for specific physical fitness components (upper and lower body strength, aerobic endurance) in the PE + CCT group, as well as mindfulness (FFMQ global score) in the MBSR + CCT group, confirm the effectiveness of the interventions in achieving their intended targets. Effect sizes for these outcomes ranged from moderate to large. In contrast, the CC and ITT analyses showed significant effects only for lower limb strength and aerobic capacity. This discrepancy likely stems from the inclusion of all participants in these analyses, regardless of their adherence to the intervention protocols. However, inconsistencies in the findings for upper body strength and mindfulness across analyses limit their robustness and warrant cautious interpretation.

In examining mediating effects on primary outcomes, we found that, in the PP sample, improvements in global FFMQ scores mediated reductions in BDI-II scores in the MBSR + CCT group compared to the PE + CCT group. This outcome aligns with our expectations and clarifies mechanisms through which MBSR interventions may enhance emotional well-being. However, contrary to our expectations, fitness improvements did not mediate cognitive gains in the PE + CCT group. This discrepancy may result from the specific fitness measures employed and limitations inherent to the online administration of the SFT battery.

Intervention adherence

Adherence to the interventions was high, with nearly 80 % of participants completing more than 80 % of the sessions, suggesting that the programs were both feasible and well-received. A qualitative sub-study within the same project supports this finding, with participants describing the activities as engaging and meaningful for their recovery [19]. This positive engagement may also reflect the characteristics of our sample, which consisted primarily of younger individuals who, despite some post-stroke difficulties, had recovered relatively well. In contrast, a systematic review reported high attrition rates for standard MBSR courses in stroke samples [5]. This discrepancy suggests that our findings may not generalize to individuals with more severe deficits, for whom session length and other standard elements may pose significant challenges. Recent studies have addressed this by adapting MBSR for participants with more pronounced symptoms [50].

Limitations

Our study has several limitations that warrant caution in interpreting the results. First, our sample was relatively young (mean age 57.7 years vs. >65 in typical stroke epidemiology [1]) and mildly impaired. We excluded individuals with severe cognitive deficits or major aphasia; cases of moderate-to-severe depression or physical disability were underrepresented. Consequently, our findings primarily pertain to younger individuals who have experienced a stroke and have mild impairments. This limited impairment range also raises the possibility of a ceiling effect that may have obscured larger treatment benefits. Second, the simple randomization strategy led to imbalances in specific baseline characteristics, such as stroke chronicity and depression levels. Although sensitivity analyses indicated that these imbalances did not alter the main conclusions, their influence on outcomes cannot be entirely ruled out. Third, the combined-intervention groups received more intervention time and structured social interaction than the CCT-only group, which may partly explain their superior effects. Fourth, the study design lacked a passive control group and included CCT in all conditions, precluding isolation of the specific effects of cognitive training from non-specific improvements such as spontaneous recovery or test–retest learning. Fifth, several deviations from the original protocol occurred, including broader eligibility criteria and revised outcome measures. Although these changes were documented and justified, and sensitivity analyses yielded consistent conclusions, they may still introduce bias. Sixth, the anticipated effect size for outcomes such as the impact of PE on cognition may have been too optimistic, potentially leaving the study underpowered to detect small to moderate effects with clinical relevance. Seventh, since outcomes were assessed only at baseline and post-intervention (12 weeks), the absence of longer-term follow-up prevents conclusions about sustainability. Finally, the online format may have compromised supervision and standardization, potentially affecting data quality, intervention fidelity, and overall effectiveness.

Conclusions

The combined interventions, MBSR + CCT and PE + CCT, did not demonstrate significant advantages over CCT alone on primary cognitive and emotional outcomes. Several analytical approaches, including multiple imputation analyses consistent with the ITT principle, supported this conclusion. Several factors may account for the lack of significant between-group differences, including participant characteristics, intervention parameters, and aspects of study design. Despite the absence of significant differences in primary outcomes, each combined intervention demonstrated positive effects in its specific target domain: mindfulness for MBSR + CCT and physical fitness for PE + CCT. Secondary and mediation analyses, exploratory in nature and based on PP and CC samples, suggest that PE + CCT may support specific cognitive tasks. At the same time, increases in mindfulness could mediate emotional improvements

in the MBSR + CCT group. These preliminary findings indicate that multimodal interventions may offer complementary benefits in post-stroke recovery. However, the results should not be generalized to individuals with moderate to severe deficits or significant mood disorders without further replication in these populations. Future RCTs are needed to confirm these findings, assess long-term outcomes, and determine their external validity for larger, more diverse, and clinically severe stroke populations.

Ethics statement

All procedures were conducted in accordance with the ethical standards outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki. All participants gave written informed consent. This study was approved by the Bioethics Commission of the Universitat de Barcelona (IRB00003099), the Research Ethics Committee of the Hospital Universitari Germans Trias i Pujol (PI-17–110), the Healthcare Ethics Committee from the Institut Guttmann, and the Clinical Research Ethics Committee of IDIAP Jordi Gol (19/056-P).

Author contributions

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Data availability

Deidentified individual participant data will be available upon reasonable request from the corresponding author.

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Appendix: supplementary materials

Appendix A: Recruitment, allocation, and blinding procedures; Appendix B: Interventions description; Appendix C: Adaptations for the telematic administration of the cognitive testing session; Appendix D:

Exploratory factor analysis; Appendix E: Multiple imputation; Appendix F: Sample characteristics; Appendix G: Intervention adherence; Appendix H: Between and within-group differences in the ten main variables (CC and ITT); Appendix I: Between and within-group differences in the secondary variables (PP and CC); Appendix J: Mediation analysis.

Declaration of competing interest

None.

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Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.rehab.2025.102008](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rehab.2025.102008).

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